

The effect of short time working allowance on employee assurance and motivation in accordance with the opinions of private school teachers

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Abstract. In this research, it was sought to understand the effect of the short-time working allowance received by private schools during the Covid-19/Pandemic period on employee assurance and motivation, with the opinions of the teachers who received this allowance. The sample of the study was the English teachers working in a private school in Antalya, Döşemealtı. Most of the teachers who participated in the interview stated that the short-time working allowance affected their assurance and motivation negatively. They stated that although they worked for full time, their assurances were paid between 10-12 days a month and this would negatively affect their retirement in the future, and this period would be prolonged for almost a year and a half. In addition, they reported that they received their salaries fragmented during this process and that they experienced difficulties in that sense. Studies on short-time working allowance mostly mentioned about the benefits it provided and how it could be used legally. This study was expected to guide private school founders in terms of how the short-time working allowance affected employee motivation and assurance, and to contribute to the literature in this sense. In order to solve the problems caused by the short time working allowance, it was foreseen that the necessary research and development studies should be done before distributing the short-time working allowance to the institutions.

Keywords: Teachers, motivation, the short-time working allowance

Introduction

In the Covid-19 epidemic that affected the world, schools in 191 countries stopped face-to-face education due to the epidemic and many students started distance education. In Turkey, on March 16, 2020, schools took a one-week vacation, and then they started their first online education on March 23, 2020 (UNESCO, 2020).

Many measures were taken and bans were introduced to prevent the disease and its spread around the world. Although these measures and prohibitions varied from country to country, they continued during Covid-19 epidemic. The economic, political, cultural and psychological effects of the Covid-19 epidemic all over the world were deeply felt from the moment the disease emerged (Karaköse, Yirci, Basyigit & Kucukcakil, 2021; Karaköse & Malkoc, 2021a).

Due to the economic crisis experienced during the Covid-19 pandemic process, many workplaces went to downsize, reduce the number of workers, apply unpaid leave, reduce working hours, shut down by temporarily stopping the work, and many people became unemployed. In order to prevent this, the conditions of short-time working and short-time working allowance were simplified, enabling all employers to benefit from short-time working allowance for their employees. Short-time working means that the employee who is insured under the Unemployment Insurance Law No. 4447, the employer's employer, due to compelling reasons or the economic crisis, temporarily reduces the working hours in the institution, reduces the activities in the workplace or stops for a while, the payment of the short-time

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working allowance to the employees. regulated by the regulation regulating the procedure containing In short work, working hours can be reduced or employee contracts suspended for a certain period of time. The concept of short-time working is a form of work that provides the employee with a small income opportunity, in order to ensure the continuation of the employee, to prevent unemployment in times of crisis. The duration of short work is limited to three months, but it can be extended up to six months by the Council of Ministers in case of need. Short-time working is an application that contributes positively to the solution of problems that will arise from economic crisis and unemployment and should be applied (Seçkin, 2015).

Short time work is a conceptual phenomenon that has emerged with economic and compelling reasons. As always, private sector employees and corporate owners were most affected by the economic crisis that emerged due to the Pandemic in our country. In order to support this crisis even a little, the concept of short time work was used. Due to the economic crisis experienced with the Covid-19 Pandemic, employers' need for their employees decreased, so instead of continuing to pay wages, employers chose to terminate their employees' jobs as a solution. In order to prevent the employees from being victimized in this regard, applying for short-time working allowance provided important benefits in terms of earning a small income for the employees. The concept of short-time working provided an opportunity for them to return to their jobs after the epidemic, by preventing the dismissal of workers in the economic crisis caused by the epidemic (Bölükbaşı, 2010).

The aim of this study was to understand and interpret the effect of the short-time working allowance received by private schools during the Covid-19/Pandemic period on employee security and motivation, with the opinions of the teachers who received this allowance. At this stage of the research, motivation was defined as “internal and external desire that activates the individual, shapes his/her behaviors and ensures absenteeism”. Since the results of the study would reveal the positive and negative effects of the short-time working allowance on the motivation of the employees, this research will guide the founders of private schools to understand the effect of this allowance, which they received from their own perspective.

Within the framework of the problem statement ‘What are the effects of the short-time working allowance received by private schools during the pandemic process on employee security and motivation?’ answers were sought to the following questions:

1. How do teachers define motivation?
2. Is motivation important for both the individual and the organization? How? Why?
3. What are the factors that motivate teachers in the institution they work in?
4. What are the teachers' opinions about the short-time working allowance?
5. Does the short-time working allowance have an effect on motivation? If yes, how does it affect motivation?

Method and paradigm of research

The paradigm of this research in qualitative strand is interpretive as it is subjective and intersubjective views of the individuals (Gunbayaı & Sorm, 2018, Gunbayaı & Sorm, 2020). Accordingly, in this research descriptive case study case study design with a holistic single case was used (Yin, 2017).

A qualitative approach was chosen in this study. Because in the research, individual interviews with the participants will be made and their views on the subject will be included and it will be supported by document analysis. In this context, case study holistic single case design will be used. Case studies are deep-based studies that try to richly describe events that occur in their natural conditions, under the

constraints of time and space, using various data collection tools (Hancock & Algozzine, 2006, Yin, 2017).

Sampling

This research was conducted between 1 September and 31 December in the first half of the 2021-2022 academic year. The population of the research consisted of the teachers working in Bahçeşehir College Parkorman Campus in Antalya, Döşemealtı. In the research, convenient sampling, which is one of the purposeful sampling techniques, was used, adding speed and practicality to research. Because in this method, the researcher chooses a situation that is close to him and easy to access (Palys, 2008). The study group of the research consisted of 5 English teachers on voluntary basis. (Table 1).

Table 1.

Distribution of demographic variables of the participants

Participants	Status	Branch	School Type	Seniority	Graduate
A	Teacher	English	Primary	10 years	English Language Teaching
B	Teacher	English	Middle	11 years	English Language Teaching
C	Teacher	English	Primary	12 years	American Culture and Literature
D	Teacher	English	Middle	13 years	English Language and Literature
E	Teacher	English	Middle	18 years	English Language Teaching

Data collection

Semi-structured individual and focus group interviews were used to reveal how the short-time working allowance affected employee motivation in line with teacher opinions. Before the interview questions were prepared, national and international literature review was carried out on the research topic. In addition to interview, documents were also used in data collection. The data related to the research were collected from the teachers through interviews between October 26 and December 31. A recording device was used to record and keep data during the interview.

Ethical procedures

Scientific research ethics were followed at all stages of the research: (1) ethics committee approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 14 decision numbered 379 on November 4th, 2021 and (2) an informed consent form was obtained from the participants before the interview.

Validity and reliability of the research

In order to increase the internal and external validity and reliability based on the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability, (Lincoln and Guba, 1985) of the qualitative data, followings were carried out: (1) In order to increase the internal validity (credibility) of the research, In addition to interview, documents were also used in data collection and the records kept at the end of the interviews were controlled by the participants to understand the research problem comprehensively, (2) in order to increase the external validity (transferability) of the research, a purposive sampling method was chosen based on voluntarism to get opinions and experiences, (3) in order to increase the internal reliability (confirmability) of the research data were coded by two independent researchers and Cohen's kappa coefficient was calculated to determine inter-rater reliability of themes.as 0.92, which was a perfect level of agreement between the coding d) In order to increase the external reliability (dependability) of the research, all data collected were kept on demand (Landis and Koach, 1977; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Cohen, Mannion and Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

Data Analysis

In qualitative strand, after the individual and focus group interviews and document collection were completed, the recorded audio files were transcribed verbatim using the NVIVO 10 software and the obtained data were analyzed with thematic, descriptive and content analysis methods. (Kelle, 1995; Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

Findings

1. The definition of motivation

In Table 2 the sub-themes related to the definition of motivation by private education teachers and the distribution of themes are given.

Table 2.

The definition of motivation by special education teachers

The definition of motivation	A	B	C	D	E
Perspective					√
Enthusiasm for work	√			√	√
Motivation		√	√		

When interpreted the definition of motivation by private education teachers in general, as in Table 2, it was seen that Enthusiasm for work took the first place. The opinions of the participants on this sub-theme are given below;

I can define motivation as the enthusiasm to work. (A1,2)

The motivation for me is to be happy in the environment you enter, especially in your classes and groups. In my opinion, if you are happy, if you do your job with love, this will motivate you and I think you will be more beneficial to your children. (D1, 2)

Like doing business lovingly, having fun and willingly. (E1, 2)

Later, another sub-theme regarding the definition of motivation was motivation. The opinions of the participants on this theme are given below:

In other words, I can explain it as being motivated: In other words, something needs to motivate you so that your motivation needs to increase.(B1, 3)

An actuation. Making progress to make positive progress.(C1, 2)

Another sub-theme was perspective regarding the definition of motivation. The opinions of the participants on these themes are given below:

Actually, perspective is motivation for me. If you want, if you want to enjoy something or if you want to have fun, you are more motivated and you do it more sincerely.(E1,1)

When we interpreted the realities of the teachers on the definition of motivation, we can understand that the most important factor that caused the employee to do his/her job with pleasure, enjoyment and pleasure was the motivation that motivated the employee in his/her performance to increase the success of the institution.

2. The importance of motivation for the institution and the individual

In Table 3 the sub-themes related to the importance of motivation for the institution and the individual by private education school teachers and the distribution of sub-themes are given.

Table 3.

The importance of motivation for the institution and the individual

The importance of motivation	A	B	C	D	E
In terms of working conditions and corporate success		√			
In terms of being happy and performing better			√	√	√
In terms of respect, support and financial dimension	√				

When interpreted the importance of motivation for the institution and the individual by private education teachers in general, as in Table 3, it was seen that in terms of being happy and performing better took the first place. The opinions of the participants on this sub-theme are given below:

It is important. People work better if they are happy.(C1,2)

Of course it matters. Because if we are happy, of course the institution will benefit from it. As long as we are happy, they will be happy in the organization and receive positive energy, so their recycling will be good for them and us.(D1,2)

... motivation is very important because it makes you not get tired of your work, it makes you have more fun, it makes you happy in life. And this affects every part of your life because you already work many hours a day. This is a very important reason for the institution because the more motivated you are, the more productive you become.(E1,2)

Later, in terms of working conditions and corporate success, and in terms of respect, support and financial dimension were mentioned. The opinions of the participants on those sub-theme are given below;

Of course it matters. Because it is important in terms of working conditions. In other words, when there is no motivation, unfortunately, we cannot show the expected success. However, when motivation is low and high, the desired goals are achieved in terms of both students and increasing the success of the institution.(B1,1)

It is of course important to me and to the institution. My personal opinion, that is, if I need to explain the details, the support given in the school, the respect for my job, the respect for me personally, besides that, of course, the financial return is motivation for me. (A1, 3)

When we interpreted the teachers' views on the importance of motivation for the individual and the institution, we understood that motivation was important in activating the employee and ensuring that he or she exhibit the desired behavior in accordance with the objectives of the institution. Motivation is important for the employee to enjoy his job and be happy in his job. As long as the employee is happy in his job, he will contribute to the effectiveness of the institution. Low and high motivation affects the success of both the institution and the students. The working conditions offered to the employee showed us that the person did his/her job with or without pleasure. The working conditions offered to the employees within the institution were important in their motivation. Since an employee working in bad conditions first expects basic needs to be satisfied, student and school will be next for him or her. As it was understood from the definition and importance of motivation, it is necessary to motivate the employees internally and externally in order to mobilize the employees in line with the goals of the organization in educational institutions whose input and output are human. The more the employee is satisfied with the institution and the environment he loves, the more he acts for the benefit of the institution.

3. Factors that motivate teachers in their institutions

In Table 4 the sub-themes related to factors that motivated private teachers in their institutions and the distribution of sub-themes are given.

Table 4.

Factors that motivate private school teachers

Factors that motivate private school teachers	A	B	C	D	E
Parents		√			
Being appreciated			√		√
Healthy working conditions, respect and support	√				
Students		√			√
Materiality			√	√	
Social relations within the institution			√		√
The extent to which requests can be fulfilled				√	
Individual success					√

When interpreted the factors that motivated private teachers in general as in Table 4, it was seen that being appreciated, students, materiality and social relations within the institution took the first place. The opinions of the participants on those sub-themes are given below:

The organization's value to people. (C2.2)

Of course, the appreciation of others is an additional event. It would be better if it did. Anything the school does can actually motivate you... (E2,2)

In other words, both the student motivates and the student does not. In other words, when you experience a positive and negative situation with them, that motivation event completely changes mutually.(B2,4)

... children's success ... children's success can really have a very good effect on people. The fact that they love you, for example, that they can touch you. It is very nice that people can touch each other's souls.(E2,4)

First of all, of course, that the salaries are paid in full. (C2,5)

Number one and most importantly, if we are happy about something financially, we stay anyway. (D2,5)

My friends are fine. (C2.6)

My colleagues. (E2, 6)

Later, the themes of parents, healthy working conditions, respect and support, the extent to which requests can be fulfilled and individual success followed. The opinions of the participants on those sub-themes are given below:

It is both motivating and not motivating. In other words, when you experience a positive and negative situation with them, that motivation event completely changes mutually. (B2.1)

If I can work in a healthy environment, if my work is respected, if I need any support, if that support is met, these are motivating things for me. (A2,3)

Secondly, to the extent that they can fulfill our wishes, of course, our motivation and motivation increase. (D2.7)

...then I don't feel unsuccessful, that is, I don't feel successful in any of the activities I do or something...(E2,8)

When we interpreted the factors that motivated the employee in the institution, we understood that many factors, not just one thing, were effective in activating the individual in the desired direction. For example, we cannot expect the organization to fulfill its goals by merely satisfying the employee in monetary terms. Humans have a complex structure. It is necessary to consider multi-faceted in mobilizing the employees in desired direction. We should know that we cannot motivate the employee with only internal or external motivation factors, and it is necessary to consider all possibilities internally and externally.

4. Short-time working allowance

In Table 4 the sub-themes related to the views of the private school teachers on short-time working allowance and the distribution of sub-themes are given.

Table 5.

Short-time working allowance

Short-time working allowance	A	B	C	D	E
Insufficient number of insurance premium days despite working		√		√	√
The risk of being unemployed		√			
Positive for the organization, negative for the employee			√	√	√
Fragmentary and incomplete receipt of salary				√	
Online education process	√		√		

When interpreted the views of the private school teachers on short-time working allowance in general as in Table 5, it was seen that insufficient number of insurance premium days despite working and positive for the organization, negative for the employee took the first place. The opinions of the participants on those sub-themes are given below:

...in the short-time working allowance, of course, it would be better if it was not given, so no one paid my premium day count, for example, half and half, but was there any other option, unfortunately there was no other option. (B3.1)

It also affected our insurance. Well, 3-4 days. Even though I am an 8th grade teacher, even though I came fully during the pandemic process, he only slept 3 days out of the 5 days I came every week or because it seemed like this 3-4 days a month, so this situation affected us. (D3.1)

Because, inevitably, your working hours did not seem as though we were online zooming from home. So it doesn't appear in systems. This was a somewhat disturbing event. (E3,1)

Of course, it was done to protect institutions, but in a way, it is a negative situation for us. (C3.3)

So there were occasional setbacks. Therefore, in my opinion, it was not an efficient application. On the contrary, we suffered more (D3,3)

It was a very, very good thing the government did. But what a good effect this has had for us is a question mark. Because, inevitably, your working hours did not seem as though we were online zooming from home. (E3,3)

Then Online education process related to the views of the private school teachers on short-time working allowance followed. The opinions of the participants on this sub-theme are given below:

We continued to work. online. Again, we did our lessons in a verb day. (A3.5)

We worked. We worked for 5 days. We had lessons every day. (C3.5)

Finally, the themes of the risk of being unemployed and fragmentary and incomplete receipt of salary related to of the private school teachers on short-time working allowance followed. The opinions of the participants on those sub-themes are given below:

In other words, when we look at the private sector now, I thought that the event would go to a very different dimension, at first, when the pandemic started, our probability of being unemployed was very high. Actually, to be honest, I'm more glad that I'm not unemployed. (B3,2)

... as far as I know from many of my friends working at private schools, they did not receive a short-time working allowance, so they continued to receive their salaries as normal, but of course, this affected us a lot as we received it in 3 parts. Because he went to bed late and we got it in 3 parts, and that short-time working allowance was also reduced from our own normal salary. We missed out. (D3,4)

When the opinions of the teachers about the short-time working allowance were interpreted, it was seen that the allowance was positive and even supportive for the institution and its owners, but it had negative effects for the employees. We can understand that teachers benefited from this allowance even though they worked, and in case of employment, their insurance was incomplete, their salaries were fragmented from both the short-time working allowance and the institution, thus causing victimization of the employees in many ways.

In addition, the information in the documents examined supported the theme of "receiving the salary fragmentary and incomplete". It proved that the salaries were paid and topped up from the Unemployment Insurance Fund and thus the salaries were received in 3 parts.

At the same time, the information in the documents examined supported the theme of "Insufficient number of insurance premium days despite working". It was seen that the number of monthly insurance premium days of teachers who taught online during school hours for a month was 10 days. Unfortunately, the number of insurance days during the short-time working allowance was shown in this way. This supported the fact that teachers were victims of appearing to be less insured for almost half of a year and a half, due to their underpaid insurance despite working. From another point of view, the fact that teachers were not unemployed in this process due to the economic crisis was what they got to do.

5. The effect of short-time working allowance on motivation

In Table 4 the sub-themes related to the views of the private school teachers on the effect of short-time working allowance on motivation and the distribution of sub-themes are given. The opinions of the participants on this theme are given below:

Table 6.

The effect of short-time working allowance on motivation

The effect of short-time working allowance on motivation	A	B	C	D	E
Positive effect on retirement					√
Positive effect due to being employed during crisis		√			
Negative effect on motivation	√			√	
Insurance motivation			√		

When analyzed the views of the private school teachers on the effect of short-time working allowance on motivation, negative effect on motivation took the first place. The opinions of the participants on this theme are given below:

But of course, what has happened now has happened and does it affect your motivation? Especially this year, our motivation is negatively affected. But as I said, I don't think much will change. (OG-C2,4)

Nothing will change, but since I think it will affect us in the long run, of course it reduces our motivation. But right now, of course, there is nothing we can do, everyone has to work, everyone has to continue in some way, but we will see the future together, but I am sure that this will not make us happy. (OG-D2,4)

Later the themes of positive effect on retirement, positive effect due to being employed during crisis, insurance motivation related to the views of the private school teachers on the effect of short-time working allowance on motivation followed. The opinions of the participants on this theme are given below:

... improvement is in question. But it is said that there will be a study on this. I hope he has the hope of working, so I think it's in everyone, especially I researched a lot. If something like that happens, of course, these things will be forgotten in a way, but if it is not done, of course, I don't think that anyone will be happy about it in the future when we retire. (OG-B2.1)

... the schools continue in a way, the institutions continue in a way, the school is not something like a factory that works today and does not work the next day, because education continues all the time, I think from today on, I am expecting a law, a law will come out or something will happen, I hope that at least the days are counted as the time we work. (OG-E2.2)

At the moment, I seem to have worked half a year, 1.5 years, as I see it. This naturally affects me. Impact my workforce. It doesn't affect my workforce, but it does affect it as motivation. In other words, as intrinsic motivation... (OG-A2,3)

When we interpreted teachers' opinions about the effect of extending the retirement period for more than one year on motivation, we can understand that it negatively affected motivation. That the institution did not need this allowance but had it without thinking, It prevented employees from thinking positively about their institutions.

5. Findings regarding the focus group discussion

In addition to individual interviews with participants A, B, C, D, E, a focus group meeting was held on 20 December at 21:22, by asking two questions over the Zoom (online connection) platform, allowing each participant to answer. Their views were categorized under themes and shown in tables.

Findings regarding the first focus group interview question

The first focus group interview question of the research was “Did the fact that you seem to be insured for a few days a month even though you work affect your motivation? How?”. Table 7 shows the teachers' views on how being insured for a few days affected motivation and the findings regarding the distribution of sub-themes.

Table 7.

The effect of appearing insured for a few days a month despite working on motivation

The effect of appearing insured on motivation	A	B	C	D	E
No effect on motivation		√			√
Negatively affected motivation	√		√	√	
Affected negatively in terms of insurance			√	√	

In Table 7, when the opinions of teachers about the effect of being insured for a few days a month while they worked on motivation were examined, it was seen that it had a negative impact on motivation in the first place. The opinions of the participants on this subject are as follows:

...if I work in a specific institution with a fixed salary and on fixed days, of course, I would like my insurance to be paid in full. And when my insurance is not paid even though I am still working continuously, this naturally affects me. (OG-A1, 2)

There is only a situation where our own morale deteriorates, otherwise there is no question of people working with children projecting them onto those innocent children. But it was a lack of motivation for us personally.(OG-C1, 2)

...I think it is a really demotivating event when we think about it, because I myself, for example, came to 8's last year, 5 days a week, even if you came 3 days a week, he somehow made half insurance, and this of course affected us. Of course, as we said, we did not reflect it on the children as other friends said, but as long as it did, it really affected me negatively every time we checked and saw it. (OG-D1, 2)

Later, there were opinions that it did not affect the motivation and negatively affected the insurance. The opinions of the participants on this subject are as follows:

As I mentioned before, it did not affect my motivation. Because I don't think there is much that can be done in this process. If some rights are given to some people, these people can use these rights very comfortably. I am a person who always advocates this.(OG-B1, 1)

From my point of view, has mine been too low, no. I always hoped that it would change and I was always expecting, a law will come out and such a thing will be said and these insurances seem to be full and I am still in that expectation and I still have such hope. (OG-E1,1)

...the fact that we worked full time, that is, 5 days, and the insurance was paid less, affected us negatively in terms of time, that is, the insurance time. Of course, it is also unfair to work and get half insurance in this way, of course, at the same time. (OG-C1, 3)

...even if you come 5 days a week, 3 days a week, he somehow made half insurance and this of course affected us. Of course, as we said, we did not reflect it on the children as other friends said, but as long as it did, it really affected me negatively every time we checked and saw it. (OG-D1, 3)

As we can see from the opinions of the teachers, the lack of insurance even though they were working had a negative impact on their motivation. It caused a decrease in the motivation to work and negatively affected internal motivation. Even though they were working, they considered the underpayment of insurance as an injustice done to them by the institution as an employee.

Findings regarding the second focus group interview

The second focus group interview question of the research was “Has the short-time working allowance extended your retirement period for more than one year, affecting your motivation? How? The distribution of the sub-themes related to the teachers' views on the effect of the short-time working allowance extending their retirement period for more than one year on motivation were formed and the findings are shown in Table 8.

Table 7.

The effect of short-time working allowance on motivation to extend the retirement period for more than one year

The effect of short-time working allowance on motivation	A	B	C	D	E
Unless improvements are made in this regard, it will affect the employee negatively		√			
Expecting to make up for missed days					√

Negative effect on intrinsic motivation	√	
Negative effect on motivation		√ √

In Table 7, when we analyzed at the teachers' views on the effect of extending the retirement period for more than one year due to the allowance on motivation, the negative effect on motivation took the first place. The opinions of the participants on this subject are as follows:

But of course, what has happened now has happened and does it affect your motivation? Especially this year, our motivation is negatively affected. But as I said, I don't think much will change. (OG-C2,4)

Nothing will change, but since I think it will affect us in the long run, of course it reduces our motivation. But right now, of course, there is nothing we can do, everyone has to work, everyone has to continue in some way, but we will see the future together, but I am sure that this will not make us happy. (OG-D2,4)

Later, the sub-themes of 'unless improvements are made in this regard, it will affect the employee negatively', expecting to make up for missed days and negative effect on intrinsic motivation followed. The opinions of the participants on this subject are as follows

:...it is possible that improvements will be made. But it is said that there will be a study on this. I hope he has the hope of working, so I think it's in everyone, especially I researched a lot. If something like that happens, of course, these things will be forgotten in a way, but if it is not done, of course, I don't think that anyone will be happy about it in the future when we retire. (OG-B2.1)

... the schools continue in a way, the institutions continue in a way, the school is not something like a factory that works today and does not work the next day, because education continues all the time, I think from today on, I am expecting a law, a law will come out or something will happen, I hope that at least the days are counted as the time we work. (OG-E2.2)

At the moment, I seem to have worked half a year, 1.5 years, as I see it. This naturally affects me. Impact my workforce. It doesn't affect my workforce, but it does affect it as motivation. In other words, as intrinsic motivation... (OG-A2,3)

When we examined the teachers' opinions about the effect of extending the retirement period for more than one year on motivation, we understood that it negatively affected motivation. Although it was expected that something would change, the thought that there would be no regulation regarding these missing days also has a depressing effect on internal motivation.

Discussion and Conclusion

In this research, it was tried to explain how the short-time working allowance received by private schools during the Covid-19 pandemic process affects employee security and motivation, with the views of teachers working in private schools. In the study, the definition of motivation, its importance for the institution and the individual, the factors that motivate the employees in the institution, the opinions of the teachers about the short-time work allowance, the effect of the short-time work allowance on the motivation were tried to be interpreted by making theme analysis, descriptive analysis and content analysis.

In educational institutions whose inputs and outputs are human, motivation is an important tool in motivating the employee in activating the desired direction in line with the goals of the organization, increasing the success of the student and the institution affiliated to it. The success of the institution depends on how willing and enthusiastic the employees are in performing that job, how fondly they do their job and to what extent they can meet their expectations. Motivation is very important for both the organization and the employee. Because realizing the goals of the institution depends on the

performance of the employee. For this, the more motivated the employee is, the more successful he will try to perform his job in the direction of motivation. Many factors such as providing healthy and reliable working conditions in the institution, respect for the employee and his or her job, appreciation of his or her performance by the institution and its managers, as well as being able to provide a financial income that will not leave him in a difficult situation, are positive in the motivation and motivation of the employee in realizing the goals of the organization. We cannot expect a person working in an environment where these are not provided to act in the direction of realizing the goals of the organization. For this, we should not forget that instead of thinking unilaterally in motivating the employee, both internal and external motivational elements are necessary in activating that person. For example, we cannot increase the salary of an employee who does not need financial support to perform better. From the point of view of corporate owners and managers, they need to know their employees well and know when and how to motivate them. Humans have a complex structure, unfortunately it is impossible to mobilize everyone with a single motivation tool.

As Maslow mentioned in the pyramid of needs, as long as the individual meets his needs, he can move on to the next need. In educational institutions whose key element is human, motivation is an important tool in motivating the employee to act in the desired direction in line with the goals of the organization, increasing the success of the student and the institution affiliated with it. The success of the institution depends on how willing and enthusiastic the employees are in performing that job, how fondly they do their job and to what extent they can meet their expectations. Motivation is very important for both the organization and the employee. Because realizing the goals of the institution depends on the performance of the employee. Therefore, the more motivated the employee is, the more successful he or she will try to perform his job in the direction of motivation. Many factors such as providing healthy and reliable working conditions in the institution, respect for the employee and his or her job, appreciation of his or her performance by the institution and its managers, as well as being able to provide a financial income that will not leave him or her in a difficult situation, are positive and will make an impact. in the motivation and motivation of the employee in realizing the goals of the organization. We cannot expect a person working in an environment where these are not provided to act in the direction of realizing the goals of the organization. Thus, we should not forget that instead of thinking individually in motivating the employee, both internal and external motivational elements are necessary in activating that person. For example, we cannot increase the salary of an employee who does not need financial support to perform better. From the point of view of corporate owners and managers, they need to know their employees well and know when and how to motivate them. Humans have a complex structure, unfortunately it is impossible to mobilize everyone with a single motivation tool. As Maslow mentioned in the pyramid of needs, as long as the individual meets his or her needs, he or she can move on to the next need. Unsatisfied need always creates dissatisfaction and unhappiness in the individual, which will affect the performance of that person, indirectly, but not directly, negatively affecting the success of the student and the institution.

The employee first expects his or her basic needs to be satisfied in the institution. A healthy and reliable work environment, satisfying his/her needs in terms of food and beverage, being satisfied with the salary he/she receives, receiving his/her salary regularly without delay, having the insurance required to guarantee his/her future on a regular basis. . As long as these basic needs are met to the desired extent, other steps can be taken. As an institution, it is necessary to know the needs of the employees and to motivate and support them accordingly. In realizing a more effective teaching process, identifying the motivational factors is an important element in activating that person in the desired direction. When we look at the factors that motivate the individual in the study, respectively, parents, students, healthy working conditions, the degree of meeting the needs, materiality, meeting the job security (insurance) in order to guarantee the future and not victimizing the individual, appreciating the performance, respecting the person and his work, social relations within the institution and such many factors motivating the employee should be considered together.

According to Brownell and Tanner (2012), teacher motivation depends on a number of factors such as payment, workload, promotion, further education and professional development opportunity,

institutional and institutional environment location, relationship with society, student behavior and service conditions. Our findings in the context of motivational factors were similar to the results of Brownell and Tanner's (2012) study. At the same time, a study conducted by Rasheed, Aslam, and Serwar (2010) supported the findings of our study. In the study of Rasheed, Aslam, and Serwar (2010), various motivational sources and factors for teachers in high schools were discussed with a comparative and relational approach. According to the results of the study, although salaries, tuition fees and additional bonuses were important sources of motivation for teachers, they revealed that there were different intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors that affected teachers' motivation in their schools.

When we return to Maslow's pyramid of needs, it is expected that the basic needs of the employee will be satisfied primarily. In fact, these basic needs are the needs that are obligatory for the employee, which are not left to the will of the person and do not offer the opportunity to choose. Housing, job security, insurance, salary, food and beverage, etc. With the arrival of the pandemic in Turkey, especially in schools, the epidemic that emerged during the Covid-19 pandemic period and the economic problems it brought with it, unfortunately, caused the basic needs, which were the lowest step of our pyramid of needs, which we saw as obligatory to be met, not being met. Many businesses closed indefinitely. Public schools continued their education through EBA [Education Information Network] and television. In addition, with the online applications they bought in private schools, they taught a verb online during the week, just like in face-to-face education.

In order to alleviate the economic crisis experienced by the state, the economic stability shield package was announced. With the short-time working allowance that came out of this practice, the institutions were prevented from dismissing their employees, and even with the allowance support, the burden of the institution owners in economic distress was slightly alleviated. When we thought about it, it was actually seen as a positive practice for the institution and the employee. However, the purpose of the short-time working allowance was to support both the employee and the owner of the institution, albeit a little, economically, instead of dismissing the employee whose working hours were reduced. The benefit of this short-time working allowance by the workplaces was beneficial for both the institution and the employee. But when we thought about it, it was positive for private schools to receive this allowance, but when we thought about it from the point of view of working teachers, it was negative. The owners of private schools never thought that this short-time working allowance, which they thought from their own perspective, would put their employees in a difficult situation. As it could be understood from the findings of the study, private school teachers were negatively affected by the short-time working allowance. Unfortunately, job security (insurance) and salary step, which are the basic needs of motivation, which we consider important for the employee, negatively affected the motivation of the employee during this short-time working allowance. And this basic need could not be satisfied during the short-time working allowance.

Private school teachers who continued to work as the short-time working allowance provided was paid from the employee's unemployment fund. As stated by the teachers participating in the study, they appeared to be insured for only 10-12 days a month, even though they provided online training. The practice of short-time working allowance, which lasted for almost one and a half years, caused private school teachers to pay less than half of their insurance. However, in this process, educational institutions did not lose students. As the participants expressed in the individual interviews, private schools did not need this short-time working allowance. As a right offered to everyone, they also benefited from this right. In this process, the founders of private schools did not think that the motivation of the teachers they worked with, their loyalty to the institution was damaged, and the fact that their insurance was not paid unjustly even though they were working was an obstacle to their retirement. The studies and results in the literature in accordance with the results of this study within the scope of short-time working allowance included:

As a result, the short-time working allowance that Private Schools received during the pandemic period greatly reduced the internal and external motivation of their teachers as employees. It not only took them back a year and a half in terms of job security, but also extended their retirement longer. Accordingly,

In the study conducted by Aydoğan (2010), the economic crises experienced in Turkey and the short-time working allowance used as a means of preventing crises were mentioned. Unemployment and bankruptcy of companies occur in economic crises. Some measures are taken by the state in order to prevent these negativities and to affect the employees and employers in the least possible way. One of them is the short-time working allowance. It is stated that short-time working allowance is a legal solution applied by businesses in crisis or compelling reasons.

In another study conducted by Demir (2021), it was stated that the economic crisis had the most critical impact on employee life. It was emphasized that legal regulations were needed to eliminate the negativities that occurred in the face of changes in working life. In line with this need, short-time working was used to alleviate the economic dimension during the crisis. Although short-time work was important in sustaining the economy during the crisis, many problems arose from this practice and appropriation. In this study, details about the legal dimensions of short-time work and short-time work allowance, problems and suggestions arising from short-time work were given.

In one another study by Başığit (2020), the concept of short work was mentioned within the scope of the effects of the Covid-19 epidemic on employee life. It was mentioned that Covid-19 was the first major epidemic of the century, spreading in 2019 and negatively affecting working life as of 2020. Due to the measures taken, the working life of the workers has been interrupted. Production came to a standstill and the manufacturer was adversely affected. One of the preventive measures of the negative effects of the epidemic was the practice of short working. It included determining the effects of the epidemic on working life and examining the regulations for limiting its negative aspects within the scope of labor law.

To sum up, in the studies carried out by the researchers, in general, the duration of the Covid-19 pandemic, the negative impact of the pandemic on employee life, motivation and the economy, the content of the short-time working allowance applied in this process, its benefits to the businesses and the problems that arose were mentioned. However, studies covering these topics were generally based on working in businesses and teachers in schools. Specifically, the effect of the short-time working allowance received by private schools during the Covid-19 process on private school teachers was not emphasized. With the findings and results of this study, it is thought that it will provide an idea to the readers and especially the private school founders in terms of seeing how the allowance they received from their own perspective affected the teaching negatively, and it will fill such a gap in the literature.

Recommendations

In consistent with the results obtained, following suggestions can be put forward:

This research was conducted in a single district and private school based on the opinions of teachers. More comprehensively, by taking the opinions of school founders in other districts and private schools, participants can be selected as teachers and founders in order to understand why they received this allowance.

Private schools could benefit from the short-time working allowance like other workplaces, but changes could be made in its content. Since the working hours of the teachers do not decrease during the short working period, an article can be added that the insurance should be fully paid by the institution. In this way, the teacher will not be victimized.

Before the short-time working allowance is given, a research and development study can be done in terms of the needs of the institutions. In this way, institutions that really need it can benefit from this appropriation.

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Ethical approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**The Effect of Short Time Working Allowance on Employee Assurance And Motivation In Accordance With The Opinions of Private School Teachers**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data. “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Ethics committee approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 14 decision numbered 379 on November 4th, 2021.